

TERMINOLOGICAL COMPONENT OF TRANSLATION WORK

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The emergence of political environment personality society came into being and always in one form or another accompanies its development. The study of political science is political institution and movements as well the way to understanding in politics itself starts. Politics and the nature of the state

The political environment is big to understand is important. In community life important political environment, various social sciences - economic theory, law, sociology, psychology and also linguists, including linguists-translators attracts attention.

First of all, the definition of the word politics if we give it, it is clear and understandable Comment by Uzbekistan National we found it permissible to quote from the encyclopedia.

As explained in this source: "Politics is the art of state management. Politics is different socio-political institutions, social strata, classes and groups related to the relationship between its essence is state power forms, implementation and manage. Politics is broad meaning the political system of society, political life, state power, its internal and external activities, political organizations and movements attitude to power, in its management realization of political interests expresses in priority directions"

Political texts include speeches by public figures; international, governmental and public organizations publications; struggle for peace, international de-escalation, arms reduction and restriction, national liberation actions, economic relations articles, and etc.

Syntactic tools play an active role in the works of political literature. They have the following features: a) the absence of long complex sentences b) the presence of a sentence, the beginning of the letter, the exact order of the head chain c) the presence of parallelisms (as well as synonyms). In this way, it is necessary to recognize the specificity of the style, but the ability to express compression. g) repetition of words, phrases, sentences that are important in content. In terms of genre, socio-political materials vary in 3 groups.

Official document materials (constitutions and legislative acts, regulations, party charter, diplomatic documents - notes, declarations, communiqués, contracts and etc.)

Information-reverse materials (information notes, information materials, historical descriptions, summarizing in the form of summary of an event, articles, articles, and etc.)

Narrow-minded journalistic articles (controversial articles, Pamphlets, speeches and etc)

The classification of political terms is as follows:

Partiyalar nomi	Name of parties
O'zLiDeP O'zbekiston Liberal Demokratik Partiyasi	UzLiDeP <u>Uzbekistan Liberal Democratic Party</u>
O'zMTDP "Milliy Tiklanish" Demokratik Partiyasi	UzMTDP <u>Uzbekistan National Revival Democratic Party</u>
ASDP Adolat Sotsial Demokratik Partiyasi	ASDP <u>Justice Social Democratic Party</u>
O'zXDP	PDP

O'zbekiston Xalq Demokratik Partiyasi	<u>People's Democratic Party of Uzbekistan</u>
O'zEP	EPU
O'zbekiston ekologik partiyasi	<u>Ecological Party of Uzbekistan</u>

Union va tuzilma nomlari	Union and structure names
Shanghai hamkorlik tashkiloti	Shanghai Cooperation Organization
Markaziy Osiyo Hamkorligi	Central Asian Cooperation
Mustaqil Davlatlar Tashkiloti	Organization of Independent States
Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkiloti	United Nations
Yevropada Xavfsizlik va Hamkorlik Tashkiloti	Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe
Yevropa Ittifoqi	European Union

Siyosiy lavozim nomlari	Names of political positions
President	President
Tashqi ishlar vaziri	Minister of Foreign Affairs
Diplomat	Diplomat

Siyosiy qo'mitalar nomlari	Names of political committees
Davlat departamenti	Department of State
Davlat xavfsizlik qo'mitasi	State Security Committee
Xavfsizlik kengashi	Security Council

Jamiyat uchun falokatli faoliyat, harakat nomlari	Disastrous activities for society, action names
Terrorizm	Terrorism
Narkomaniya	Drug addiction
Ekstremizm	Extremism
Korrupsiya	Corruption
Narkoagressiya	Narco-aggression

References:

1. «O'zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi» - T.: Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti, 2004
2. Hojiev A. Lingvistik terminlarning izohli lug'ati. – T.: O'qituvchi, 1985
3. Hamidov X., Azzamova N., Turkcha ijtimoiy-falsafiy va siyosiy terminlar tarjimasiga doir, Tarjima masalalari, ilmiy maqolalar to'plami. – T.: , 2012
4. С.А.Насирова (2021). Политическая метафора (на примере материала по кадровой политике современной КНР). In Resent Scientific Investigation (pp. 69-73)